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THE ROLE OF THE SPIRITUAL HERITAGE OF EASTERN THINKERS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF AESTHETIC EDUCATION IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL ESTABLISHMENTS

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Annotation. In this article, the role of the spiritual heritage of Eastern thinkers in the development of aesthetic education among higher education students, that is, how important the spiritual heritage of our ancestors is in the process of improving aesthetic education among higher education students.

Key words: higher education, aesthetics, Eastern thinkers, Alisher Navai, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Al-Khorazmi, Al-Farghani, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, aesthetic education, spiritual heritage.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается роль духовного наследия восточных мыслителей в развитии эстетического воспитания учащихся высших учебных заведений, то есть насколько важно духовное наследие наших предков в процессе совершенствования эстетического воспитания учащихся высших учебных заведений

Ключевые слова: высшее учебное заведение, эстетика, восточные мыслители, Алишер Наваи, Абу Наср Фараби, Абу Райхан Беруни, Аль-Хорезми, Аль-Фаргани, Абу Али ибн Сина, эстетическое воспитание, духовное наследие.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada pedagogika oliy ta'lim muassalarida estetik tarbiyani rivojlantirishda sharq mutafakkirlari ma'naviy merosining o'rni, ya'ni pedagogika oliy ta'lim muassalarida estetik tarbiyani takomillashtirish jarayonida bobokolonlarimiz ma'naviy merosining nechog'lik ahamiyatli ekanligi maqola mavzusining muammosi sifatida ochib berishga harakat qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: pedagogika oliy ta'lim muassalari, estetika, sharq mutafakkirlari, Alisher Navoiy, Abu Nasr Farobiy, Abu Rayhon Beruniy, Al-Xorazmiy, Al-Farg'oniy, Abu Ali Ibn Sino, estetik tarbiya, ma'naviy meros.

Spirituality in a broad sense encompasses the concepts of enlightenment and culture. The words morality, ethics, and behavior are also Arabic words derived from the fundamental meaning of spirituality, and they are also used in the Uzbek language in their own meaning. Morality actively influences our lives and minds, and through personal dialogue determines acceptable and unacceptable, permissible and prohibited actions in human relations between good and evil, justice and injustice, kindness and cruelty.

Spiritual, moral and aesthetic education is a criterion that indicates the degree to which an individual has been able to assimilate and use all the spiritual and intellectual blessings created by society to improve his or her morality.

We, teachers, play an important role in educating the younger generation. Every nation ensures its great future by raising the younger generation in a well-rounded manner. For this, it is the demand of the present era for each person to understand himself, the path to perfection, to know the melodies of our heritage that have world significance, to have imagination, to argue, to deeply understand that they are a necessary factor in our spiritual needs.

Indeed, the concepts and teachings about the improvement and evolutionary development of natural phenomena and the improvement of aesthetic education have found their expression in the works of our scholars such as Al-Khwarizmi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Mirza Ulugbek, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur.[1] The works of these thinkers have become the scientific basis for the development of such sciences as astronomy, mathematics, geology, logic, music, metrology, ethics, medicine and botany.

The article is based on the generally accepted methods - historicality, comparative-logical analysis, sequence, and objectivity, and the specific pedagogical conditions for the formation of aesthetic education in primary school students are studied.

Determining the place of the heritage of Eastern thinkers in the formation of aesthetic education in primary school students: Abu Abdullah al-Khwarizmi (783-850 AD) Abu Abdullah Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khwarizmi is one of the Central Asian scholars who is one of the founders of world mathematics. At the beginning of the 9th century, Al-Khwarizmi began to head the "Academy of Ma'mun" (Bayt ul-Hikmat) in Baghdad with Central Asian scholars Al-Ahmad Ibn Kathir al-Farghani and Abbas ibn Jawhari [2].

The Caliph of Baghdad entrusted Ma'mun al-Khwarizmi with the task of compiling the "Map of the Earth and the Sky". Scientists conducted research on the map for 84 years. Al-Khwarizmi summarized these studies and wrote a work called "The Image of the Earth", laying the foundation for the science of geography. This work included information about the entire world, continents, oceans, poles, equator, deserts, lakes, forests and all countries, territories, the animal and plant world there, other natural resources, population, their distribution characteristics, customs, crafts, and density.

Al-Khwarizmi made a great contribution to the creation of the world's first geographical atlas (a set of maps). Al-Khwarizmi also did a lot of work in the field of astronomy. He comprehensively analyzed the astronomical tables of the Indians based on observations and compiled new astronomical tables. In it, one degree of the Earth's meridian was measured in order to determine the size of the Earth's sphere. Al-Khwarizmi's work on astronomy, his ideas about the size of the Earth,

made a great contribution to the development of astronomy in the Middle East and Europe.

The famous Uzbek mathematician Musa al-Khwarizmi is considered the "father" of modern algebra and the field of "Algorithms." "Algebra" is derived from the work "Al jabr," and "Algorithm" is named after al-Khwarizmi [3].

Abu Rayhan al-Beruni (973-1048) Abu Rayhan Muhammad ibn Ahmad al-Beruni was a great Uzbek encyclopedist and a prominent thinker of the Middle Ages and later periods.

Beruni was born in 973 in Qiyat (now the city of Berani), Khorezm. In 1004, Beruni wrote a work entitled "Relics of the Ancient Peoples", dedicated to Qabus ibn Vushmagir.

Beruni's works contain a lot of information about nature. For example, he gives information about the mineral wealth (medicinal plants, animals) of Central Asia, India and Afghanistan, their beneficial properties. Beruni's scientific views are widely covered in such works as "Mineralogy", "India", "Monuments of Ancient Peoples", "Geodesy", "Mas'ud's Law"[4].

In his work "Monuments of Ancient Peoples," Berani describes the tropical flora and fauna widespread in northern Iran. Berani's work "Kitab as-Saydana-fit-tibbi" ("Medicine in Nature") was found in a library in Bursa, Turkey in 1927.

This book contains information about more than 250 physicians, pharmacists, chemists, naturalists, historians, philosophers, and travelers.

Berani's ideas about natural and artificial selection are also noteworthy. If the Earth were completely covered by the same tree or the same animal, then there would be no room for the reproduction of animals and trees, or for the growth of trees, the scientist noted.

Berani's work "Medicine in Nature" also provides a classification of medicinal plants. Berani laid the foundation for the history of natural science with his works.

Abu Abbas al-Farghani. Astronomer, geographer, mathematician, one of the founders of spherical geometry, a great thinker who led the construction of the Baghdad and Damascus observatories, predicted solar eclipses, scientifically proved that the Earth is spherical, calculated the length of the meridian, and created an instrument for measuring the water of the Nile River.

Abu Ali ibn Sino (980-1037). The great scholar Abu Ali Ibn Sino, who made a great contribution to the development of world scientific thought, left a huge scientific legacy. Along with his in-depth study of the works of Eastern thinkers who preceded him, he diligently studied the ancient Greek medical, scientific and philosophical heritage, in particular the works of Aristotle, Ptolemy, Galen, Hippocrates, Pythagoras. Ibn Sino's book "Kitab al-qanun fittib" (The Canons of

Medicine) consists of five large books, which were fully published in Russian and Uzbek in 1956 and 1962. These books describe the theoretical sciences of medicine, such as human anatomy, physiology and hygiene, as well as knowledge related to internal diseases, surgery, pharmacology, and infectious diseases. This book has been the main reference for doctors around the world for 600 years, and much of the information in it still retains its relevance. It has been reprinted 36 times. Ibn Sina emphasized the great role of polluted water and air in the origin and spread of various infectious diseases, and recommended boiling or filtering water for consumption. He expressed his opinion about invisible “small animals” that spread diseases through various natural objects in the external environment, air, water, that is, microbes, 800 years before L. Pasteur. He expressed his views on the need for external protection, personal and social hygiene in the prevention of diseases 1000 years ago.

In conclusion, it can be said that the development of aesthetic education in primary school students is reflected in the high level of application of the acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications in practice on the role of the spiritual heritage of Eastern thinkers. One of the main directions of the development of the education system in modern society is the organization of purposeful and independent human activity in various fields. Therefore, it is possible to achieve more effective results in education by focusing on the specific pedagogical conditions for the formation of aesthetic education in primary school students, paying special attention to motivational, social, informational-content, activity, didactic factors.

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Mamaraimova Nasiba Yadgarovna. Aksilogik yondashuv asosida bo‘lajak o‘qituvchilarning nutq madaniyatini rivojlantirish metodikasi	743
Mamatov Avaz Muhiddinovich. Boshlang‘ich sinf o‘qituvchilarini hozirgi zamon sharoitida axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish ko‘nikmalarini rivojlantirishning ahamiyati	747
Alimxanova Nigoraxon Amilyevna, UzSWLU. THE ROLE OF THE SPIRITUAL HERITAGE OF EASTERN THINKERS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF AESTHETIC EDUCATION IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL ESTABLISHMENTS	749
Tangatov Bobomulla Bozorboyevich. DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM	753